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**DEVELOPING A DESIGN ETHICS COURSE FOR DESIGN
UNDERGRADUATES IN TAIWAN:
OBJECTIVE, CONTENT, PEDAGOGY, AND CURRICULUM SETUP**

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ABSTRACT

This paper proposes a required, stand-alone design ethics course for design undergraduates in Taiwan. The course structure consists of four main parts: the course objective, content, pedagogy (i.e., teaching and assessment methods), and curriculum setup. The objective is delineated in three levels: design professional behavior, design professional expertise and design professional values. The selected teaching methods include: lectures, class discussions and case studies and the assessment methods are class participation (include attendance) and written/oral report. A possible syllabus of a design ethics course with weekly teaching schedule for the field of design is proposed and the challenges for developing the design ethics course are explored.

Keywords: design ethics, ethics course, design curriculum, design education.

INTRODUCTION

Recently, some cases of plagiarism occurred in Taiwan, apparently violating ethics of the design discipline. Sharp criticisms have been raised in the media along with calls for strengthening ethics education in liberal as well as professional courses. Character education has long been an important topic in Taiwan and "Design Ethics" as a course title in undergraduate design programs in Taiwan has been used over a decade. It may indicate that design educators in Taiwan have realized that our future designers should act ethically and responsibly in the complex, globalized marketplace and society; but there is still no consensus among design schools in Taiwan on the scope and content of design ethics

(You & Lee, 2011), indicating a need for more frequent discussions and researches on this matter. Since Victor Papanek (1985) raised the ethical issues in design practices and education about 40 years ago, the discussion of ethical issues in design has been gradually growing and continuing (D'Anjou, 2010; Margolin & Margolin, 2002; Morelli, 2007; Oosterlaken, 2009; Thomas, 2006; Whiteley, 1993). However, despite the fact that there are some articles focused on ethical issues in design education (Buchanan, 2001; Lilley & Lofthouse, 2010; Szenasy, 2003), the exploration of design ethics education is nevertheless still in its early stage as compared to other disciplines such as Medicine, Engineering, and Business (Bero & Kuhlman, 2010; DuBois & Burkemper, 2002; Herkert, 2000; Musick, 1999; Ogundiran & Adebamowo, 2010; Park, 1998; Rabins, 1998; Robin, 2009; Stephan, 1999; Van de Poel et al., 2001).

Design education has a history of about 50 years in Taiwan (Yang & You, 2010); the education and research remain mainly on the traditional design scientific and practical components. Accompanying with the global environmental changes and growing expectations of society on designers educated locally, designers in Taiwan are not only facing ever increasing new challenges, but are also bearing a heavier responsibility toward the society they work in. To respond to and improve the situations, this paper aims to propose a design ethics course suitable for design undergraduates in Taiwan. The composition of this proposal is mainly based on the results of a previous research on design ethics-related course syllabi, related ethical advices from design experts, and the experiences of ethics education from design and other disciplines (You & Lee, 2011).

DESIGN ETHICS EDUCATION IN TAIWAN

Design in higher education has a history of about 50 years in Taiwan (Yang & You, 2010). The trend of design education focuses mainly on the traditional design scientific & practical components and the design ethical issues have scarcely been formally discussed and researched. However, it doesn't mean that design schools pay no attention on ethics education. Ethics education is a part of character formation, and character education has long been an important topic on the teaching agenda in Taiwan - usually treated as a liberal arts education through general knowledge such as ethology, philosophy, or even sociology or politics, contrasting to the professional and technical knowledge emphasizing specialization.

As the design profession becomes popular and well recognized in Taiwan in the 1980s (Yang et al., 2010; Yang & You, 2010) and the influence of design in our everyday life keeps growing, some design programs in colleges and universities start to ponder about how to effectively teach ethics in design and some specific design ethics courses are thence developed. Searching the keyword "Character education" in the two web-based databases, the Curriculum Upload Systems for General and Technological & Vocational Universities built by Taiwan Ministry of Education (MOE) would find that "Design Ethics" as a course title in the curricula of undergraduate design programs has been used over a decade. These design programs according to the Standard Classification of Education (SCED) of MOE, are classified into four types, namely industrial/product design, graphic/visual communication/digital media design, spatial/interior design, and general/synthetic design. Our previous research on the syllabi of design ethics-related courses in the curricula of regular 4-year undergraduate design programs during academic years 2008 and 2009 identified five topics from the parts of course objective and content. The five topics represent different perspectives on what the undergraduates need to learn in order to prepare their role in the society (You & Lee, 2011). The topics ranged from the specific (design) to the general (life) obviously indicate that some are directly adopted from the courses of traditional character education. The influence from other disciplines, such as Medicine, Engineering, and

Business, was also evidenced in this study. This is understandable since these disciplines have a longer history and hence a more mature development of ethics education. However, due to different nature and teaching goals between these disciplines, it is inefficient and inappropriate to directly adopt and apply their courses into the design discipline. On the other hand, penetrating and profound advice for design education has been given by design experts. Those concepts that have not received enough attention should be taken seriously and integrated into the design curriculum. As the influences of design affect us from many aspects, it demands not only a creative and skillful designer, but also an ethical and responsible designer for his works, not just in Taiwan but all over the world. One of the best ways to achieve this, we believe, is through education, and a well-developed design ethics course dedicated to the design field would be a good start. Thus we attempt to develop a design ethics course based on the prior research, advices from experts, and ethics education experiences from design and other disciplines.

DEVELOPING A DESIGN ETHICS COURSE

To develop a design ethics course more suitable for the design undergraduates in Taiwan, considerations are given to the most relevant components of a course: course objective, content, pedagogy (i.e., teaching and assessment method), and curriculum setup (i.e., the type of course, the year and semester taught, etc.). We agree with Van de Poel et al. (2001) that the choice of educational setup, methods and contents should be motivated by teaching goals; in our case, the course objective would be our top priority of considerations. In addition, we do not attempt to focus on only one specific type of design program, thus we establish only the core concepts or major categories of each component of the course and modularize them so that they can be more generic and flexible in use.

THE CORE CONCEPTS OF COURSE OBJECTIVE

"Design is a problem-solving activity" is a description generally accepted by academics and professions, students would learn that during their school life. But with its influences to shape our culture and society, students ought to be further aware of that

design is not just a neutral means for achieving human's ends. Design, by its nature of dealing with objects for human use, inevitably has a strong relation with ethical issues. At least three areas of ethics concerns are related: the genuineness and originality of its creation, its safety and harmlessness to the user and the public, and its greenness and sustainability to the environment and the earth as a whole. As Papanek (1985) points out:

design as a problem-solving activity can never, by definition, yield the one right answer: it will always produce an infinite number of answers, some "righter" and some "wronger." The "rightness" of any design solution will depend on the meaning with which we invest the arrangement.

That is, the solutions would be varied dependently with designers' judgment of values which gives the meaning for design, a way of thinking on how to make ethical decisions and take responsibilities. However, in practice different stakeholders are involved for multiple purposes during the design process. It leads to a more complicated effect on the ethical issues that the designers confront.

Professions from other disciplines face similar situations. The goal of medical ethics education is described as endowing physicians with "practical wisdom", not knowledge alone, and "wisdom is the realm of ethics" (Musick, 1999). The key concept in engineering ethics is the notion of "professional responsibility", a type of moral responsibility arising from special knowledge possessed by an individual (Herkert, 2000). Van de Poel et al. (2001) specifically define two goals for them to teach ethics and engineering at Delft University: the first one focuses on the correspondent knowledge and skills which enable students to develop and apply to the future professional practice; the second one implies a focus further to the social context. In addition to incubating ethical thinking, both of them emphasize the practical context in which the students exercise their skill and talent in the future.

Indeed, to put the ethical issues in the practical context for students, it would be appropriate and efficiently helpful for them to prepare for the ethical challenges in the future. In doing so, it is required to increase their ethical awareness and

deliver necessary knowledge and skills regarding the matter. In addition, the artifacts exist only with human praxis. Perkins (2005) proposes a three-level consideration of ethics for designers in the professional practice: the first level is the professional behavior in daily business interactions; the second deals with specific professional expertise needed in areas such as accessibility, usability, and environmental practices; the third level is about overall professional values – a broader framework of moral principles and obligations in life. The structure of Perkins' suggestion which covers the ethical issues individually, professionally and socially is also quite suitable for our situation in Taiwan.

Our course objective, therefore, is to progressively guide students to learn how to deal with the ethical issues in the practical context. We adopt the three levels from Perkins as the basic, professional and prospective objectives which would be deployed gradually in a course. The first level is the design professional behavior; the second level is the design professional expertise, and the third level is the design professional value (figure 1).

Figure 1. The core concepts of course objective in three levels.

TEACHING CONTENTS

Once course objective is established, the contents would then be developed accordingly. Considering the capability and suitability of our subjects, the design undergraduates, we determine to adopt a more practical perspective and exclude pure philosophical theories from our contents. Van de Poel et al. (2001) report, on their experience in

developing the Engineering ethics course, that “students had difficulty in understanding these theories. In fact, most students were unable to apply these moral theories to concrete cases.” Lawlor (2007) also argues that moral theories are generally fairly too complex to be taught in a limited time when teaching applied ethics to professionals or future professionals. We agree with them as we have the same concerns. We do recognize the effectiveness of philosophical theories on ethical reasoning and decision-making, but maybe it is more suitable for graduates. In the following sections, the contents corresponding to the three levels of objective would be further explained.

The first level: design professional behavior

The first level represents the basic objective, is about the design professional behavior. The design professional behavior, as Perkins describes, is about how designers conduct their business interactions and activities ethically. He suggests adopting the various codes of ethics from the design organizations as the ethical guideline, noting that they “can be very helpful in educating new designers who are just entering the profession” (Perkins, 2005). It would be worthwhile to bring the notion of code of ethics into the class since that code of ethics is recognized as an effective content for professional ethics education (Herkert, 2000; Rabins, 1998). In Taiwan, it seems to be a missing concept yet in the society. There is no written code of ethics in the related local professional organizations of design, and neither in our prior research the concept was found in the survey. This situation has recently been noticed by Hu (2010), and a draft of a code of ethics for industrial designers in Taiwan has thus been proposed under the advice of one of this article’s authors. Her study is a suitable material for class and her work is worth for further research.

In addition to the code of conduct, we also add one more basic topic in this level, based on our prior research: laws and the regulations directly related to design practices. We take laws as the fundamental standard of conduct for designers in a society. Learning about them is not only imperative but also beneficial in practices. This can be shown by the recent cases of design plagiarism, exemplifying the negative impacts due to a lack of necessary

knowledge of the law. Those cases can also serve as appropriate materials to be presented and discussed in the class.

The second level: design professional expertise

The second level represents the professional objective, is about the design professional expertise. It is to emphasize on the design practice and its consequences. Contents of design theories and principles related to the additional professional liabilities and legal obligations, e.g. Sustainable design and Universal design, would be introduced and discussed in this level. The introductions and discussions would be comprehensive in depth and width, thus the design theories and principles should also be optional, depending on what particular professional liabilities and legal obligations are about to be probed into. Compared to the first level, this level augments the practices of design profession and specifies the professional liabilities and particular legal obligations in the practical contexts.

The third level: design professional value

The third level represents the prospective objective, is about a broader framework of moral principles and obligations in life. It is to encourage students to reflect on the ethical concerns from the professional conduct to the social aspects. Design thoughts and movements related to the issues will be discussed in this level. The issues Perkins proposed on this matter, such as the expansion of consumer culture, the increasing power of corporations, the globalization of trade, and the designer’s role, all have been discussed and explored thoroughly by Papanek (1985) and Whiteley (1993) in the distinguished books, *Design for the real world* and *Design For Society*. The insights for design on the broader issues are profound. It is worthy of our continued discussion. Moreover, since their thoughts are well-constructed by chapters, it is useful to take the advantages of the book structure as topics in the class.

TEACHING AND ASSESSMENT METHODS

Lecture, class discussion, and case studies are selected as the teaching methods based on the results of our prior study and related studies from other disciplines.

Core concepts of course objective	Level 1 Basic Design professional behavior	Level 2 Professional Design professional expertise	Level 3 Prospective Design professional value
Teaching contents	Codes of ethics and laws & regulations directly related to design practices	Design theories and principles in specific domains	Design thoughts and movements
Potential topics/issues	Codes of ethics of design organizations (alphabetical order): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • American Institute of Graphic Arts • Australian Graphic Design Association • Chartered Society of Designers • Design Institute of Australia • Industrial Designers Society of America • Industrial Designers Society of Hong Kong • International Council of Societies of Industrial Design Design-related laws & regulations: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Intellectual Property Right • Copyright Act - Creative Commons Taiwan • Patent Act • Trademark Act 	Green design/ Ecodesign/ Sustainable design <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low-impact materials • Energy efficiency • Quality and durability • Design for reuse and recycling • Design Impact Measures for total carbon footprint and life-cycle assessment • Biomimetics • Service substitution • Renewability Accessible Design / Barrier-free design/ Universal design <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Equitable use • Flexibility in use • Simple and intuitive use • Perceptible information • Tolerance for error • Low physical effort • Size and space for approach and use 	Papanek and <i>Design for the real world</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Design for the Third World • Design of teaching and training devices for the retarded, the handicapped, and the disabled • Design for medicine, surgery, dentistry, and hospital equipment • Design for experimental research • Systems design for sustaining human life under marginal conditions • Design for breakthrough concepts Whiteley and <i>Design For Society</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consumer-led Design • Green Design • Responsible Design and Ethical Consuming • Feminist Perspectives
Teaching methods	Lecture/class discussion/case studies		
Assessment methods	Class participation (including attendance)/ written/oral report		
Curriculum setup	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A stand-alone course offered in one semester • A required professional course • A senior undergraduate level course (for the third or fourth year design undergraduates) 		

Table 1. A conceptual framework for design ethics course

Lecture is the most common technique applied in teaching; class (group) discussion and case studies (method) both are a valid mechanism and popular tool for teaching ethics (DuBois & Burkemper, 2002; Herkert, 2000; Lilley & Lofthouse, 2010; Szenasy, 2003; You & Lee, 2011). Issues raised from class discussions would spur students to an ethical thinking and can be explored further as the

course unfolds. Through case studies, students engage with the scenarios that they might encounter in the future. Case studies enable students to examine and reflect upon ethical issues and connect taught theories and principles to real-world practices (Lilley & Lofthouse, 2010). The chosen assessment methods are class participation (including attendance), written

assignment and oral report. Common assessment methods such as closed question examination and quizzes are not suitable to evaluate subject like ethics where no correct answer exists. Thus the strategy is encouraging more participation thereby affecting the concepts and behaviors. Written/oral report would reveal and reflect what students have learned and comprehended in the class. In addition, Lilley & Lofthouse (2010) suggest that to support active learning and engagement the written/oral report can be done by self-assessment, written assignments (comprised of a mixture of short answer questions and longer issue-based critical essays), and group presentation (to encourage collaboration rather than competition).

CURRICULUM SETUP

Based on our prior research findings and the experience of Van de Poel et al. (2001), we suggest that a stand-alone course be dedicated to design ethics for the senior undergraduate level (the third or fourth year) design undergraduates in one semester. We agree with Van de Poel et al. that ethical issues can be addressed more intensively and professionally in a required, stand-alone course. We also agree that teaching senior students is more appropriate as they are more mature in the breadth of knowledge and life experience to appreciate the importance and meaning of the issues covered.

Finally, a conceptual framework for the design ethics course (table 1) is then built accordingly. A draft syllabus of the design ethics course with weekly teaching schedule based on the framework (table 1) is presented in table 2.

A SYLLABUS OF A DESIGN ETHICS COURSE WITH WEEKLY TEACHING SCHEDULE

The selected topics and contexts in the syllabus are as relevant as possible to the local (Taiwan) context. Evidence suggests that emotional engagement influences moral judgment (Greene et al., 2001); therefore, in our case, the content attached to the local context would hopefully provoke more emotional involvements from students and arouse more ethical thinking and

conduct. The specific issues in each of the three levels in the weekly teaching schedule should be viewed as a work in progress rather than a time-oriented goal.

CHALLENGES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF A DESIGN ETHICS COURSE

A number of questions and concerns raise with regard to the three aspects of the development of a design ethics course: the suitability and availability of teaching materials, the competence of the ethics instructors, and the placement of ethics subject in the design curriculum.

First, we face the challenge of the suitability and availability of teaching materials. The teaching content attached to the local context, in our opinion, is important since it provokes more emotional involvements of students (Greene et al., 2001), and would arouse more ethical thinking and conduct. However, the fact that there is no written code of ethics officially adopted by the related professional organizations of design in Taiwan implies that the consensus of design ethics has not yet formed in the society. It might be due to the poverty of resources and documentations related to the design ethics in the local context. As teaching ethics in design is a relatively new subject in Taiwan comparing to other countries, a short-term expedient is to adapt the materials from other countries for suitability. In a long-term development of design ethics education, it is a significant topic that needs more people to pay attention to it. Such studies as Hu's (2010) work merit a further research.

Second is about the challenges on the competence of ethics instructors. As previously mentioned that teaching ethics in design is a relatively new subject in Taiwan, instructors are likely with little experience in teaching this course. They might feel the same way as Lilley & Lofthouse (2010) report that they are ill-equipped to competently assess ethics as there are no established guidelines and the subjective nature of the subject makes it difficult to be consistent. This leads to the next challenge.

The last challenge is with regard to the placement of ethics subject in the design curriculum.

Course Syllabus for Design Ethics

Course Description

This is a senior undergraduate level course (2 credits) intended for the third or fourth year students in design college, include: industrial/product design, graphic/visual communication/digital media design, spatial/interior design, and general/synthetic design.

Learning Objective

Students who complete the work required for this course (reading, studying, thinking, writing, participating in class discussions, etc.) will be able to

1. identify a proper professional behavior and conduct, and inappropriate and illegal act in design profession;
2. improve awareness about recognizing ethical issues and making ethical decisions in design practices;
3. explore ethical obligations and ethical ideals present in the relationship between designers, member of society and environment.

Week	Topic	Week	Topic
1	Introduction of the course	10	Introduction and application of Universal design and its relation with Accessible Design/Barrier-free design
2	Introduce the concept of Codes of ethics and Codes of ethics from different organization	11	Universal design principles and the case study I
3	Class activity/discussion: write codes of ethics for design organizations in Taiwan	12	Universal design principles and the case study II
4	Introduction of Intellectual Property Right & Copyright Act	13	Whiteley and <i>Design For Society</i> : Responsible Design and Ethical Consuming/case discussion: Toyota Recall
5	Introduction of Trademark Act & Patent Act	14	Whiteley and <i>Design For Society</i> : Feminist Perspectives
6	Real-case discussion: the lawsuit of the design company and student/plagiarisms of the poster design competition to promote copyright protection and the poster of 2011YODEX	15	Papanek and <i>Design for the real world</i> : Design of teaching and training devices for the retarded, the handicapped, and the disabled/case discussion: class 2009 ID student design project
7	Introduction and application of Sustainable design and its relation with Green design/ Ecodesign	16	Papanek and <i>Design for the real world</i> : Systems design for sustaining human life under marginal conditions/case discussion: design for earthquake victims
8	Sustainable design principles and the case study I	17	End-term oral presentation I(group project)
9	Sustainable design principles and the case study II	18	End-term oral presentation II(group project)

Required Books Information

Papanek, V. (1985) *Design for the Real World: Human ecology and social change*. 2 ed. London: Thames & Hudson. ISBN: 978-0-50027-358-6

Whiteley, N. (1993) *Design for Society*. London: Reaktion. ISBN: 0-948462-47-7.

Requirements and Grades

Final grade for this course will be based on the number of "performance points" accumulated this semester by meeting the following course requirements:

1. Two papers - mid-term a redesign case study and end-term own design work assessment report (xx points each; xx points total)
 2. In-class end-term group oral presentation (xx points)
 3. Overall student presentation based on the frequency and quality of class attendance, participation and discussions (xx points)
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Table 2. A possible syllabus of a design ethics course

A stand-alone course as we now propose, in our view, will not be sufficient for preparing students adequately for their future practice. Attention to ethics across the curriculum might be necessary as well. In addition, to support and encourage the concept, symposiums and seminars dedicated to the topics of design ethics education should be held on a regular basis and supported by MOE, design professional organizations as well as educational institutions. As mentioned previously, although design ethics education has been deployed over a decade in Taiwan, it does lack for relevant and

frequent discussions and researches in the educational and professional circles. Such symposiums and seminars would provide a forum for the dissemination and exchange of up-to-date information on theoretical, generic and applied areas of design ethics and facilitate educators and professionals in teaching and studying on design ethics education.

Each of the challenges described above is critical yet arduous to the development of design ethics education in Taiwan. It requires more design educators and experts to work together to overcome.

CONCLUSION AND FURTHER RESEARCH

This paper proposes a required, stand-alone design ethics course for the third or fourth year design undergraduates in Taiwan and drafts a possible syllabus with weekly teaching schedule for the field of design. It is still a conceptual one and needs to be further clarified and modified by eliciting opinions from both design educators and students. We believe that our attempt and the result would benefit from a wider audience at this stage. In this spirit we put forward the outcome so that an improvement can be made in a further research.

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REFERENCES

- Bero, B. & Kuhlman, A. (2010) Teaching ethics to engineers: Ethical decision making parallels the engineering design process. *Science and engineering ethics*, published online: 04 June 2010. DOI: 10.1007/s11948-010-9213-7.
- Buchanan, R., (2001) The problem of character in design education: Liberal arts and professional specialization. *International Journal of Technology and Design Education*, Vol. 11, No. 1, 13-26.
- D'Anjou, P. (2010) An alternative model for ethical decision-making in design: A Sartrean approach. *Design Studies*, Vol. 32, No. 1, 45-59.
- DuBois, J. M. & Burkemper, J. (2002) Ethics education in U.S. medical schools: A study of syllabi. *Academic Medicine*, Vol. 77, No. 5, 432-437.
- Greene, J. D., Sommerville, R. B., Nystrom, L. E., Darley, J. M., & Cohen J. D. (2001) An fMRI investigation of emotional engagement in moral judgment. *Science*, Vol. 293, 2105-2108.
- Herkert, J. R. (2000) Engineering ethics education in the USA: Content, pedagogy and curriculum. *European Journal of Engineering Education*, Vol. 25, No. 4, 303-313.
- Hu, Y.C. (2010) *On professional ethics and the construction of a code of ethics for industrial designers in Taiwan*. National Yunlin University of Science and Technology, Yunlin, Taiwan. Unpublished master thesis. [in Chinese]
- Lawlor, R. (2007) Moral theories in teaching applied ethics, *Journal of Medical Ethics*, Vol. 33, 370-372.
- Lilley, D., Lofthouse, V. (2010) Teaching ethics for design for sustainable behaviour: A pilot study. *Design and Technology Education: an International Journal*, Vol. 15, No. 2, 55-68.
- Margolin, V. & Margolin, S. (2002) A "social model" of design: Issues of practice and research. *Design Issues*, Vol. 18, No. 4, 24-30.
- Morelli, N. (2007) Social innovation and new industrial contexts: Can designers "industrialize" socially responsible solutions? *Design Issues*, Vol. 23, No. 4, 3-21.
- Musick, D. W. (1999) Teaching medical ethics: A review of the literature from North American medical schools with emphasis on education. *Medicine, Health Care and Philosophy*, Vol. 2, No. 3, 239-254.
- Ogundiran, T. O. & Adebamowo, C. A. (2010) Medical ethics education: A survey of opinion of medical students in a Nigerian university. *Journal of Academic Ethics*, Vol. 8, No. 2, 85-93.
- Oosterlaken, I. (2009) Design for development: A capability approach. *Design Issues*, Vol. 25, No. 4, 91-102.
- Papaneck, V. (1985) *Design for the Real World: Human ecology and social change*. 2 ed. London: Thames & Hudson.
- Park, H. J. (1998) Can business ethics be taught?: A new model of business ethics education. *Journal of Business Ethics*, Vol. 17, No. 9/10, 965-977.
- Perkins, S. (2005) Ethics and social responsibility. *Step magazine*, Vol. 21, No. 4, retrieved February 9, 2009, from <http://www.stepsidedesign.com/STEPMagazine/Article/28481/>.
- Rabins, M. J. (1998) Teaching engineering ethics to undergraduates: Why? What? How? *Science and engineering ethics*, Vol. 4, No. 2, 291-302.
- Robin, D. (2009) Toward an applied meaning for ethics in business. *Journal of Business Ethics*, Vol. 89, No. 1, 139-150.
- Stephan, K. D. (1999) A survey of ethics-related instruction in U.S. engineering programs. *Journal of Engineering Education*, Vol. 88, No. 4, 459-464.
- Szenasy, S. S. (2003) Ethical design education: Confession of a Sixties Idealist. In: Heller, S. & Vienne, V. (Eds.). *Citizen Designer: Perspectives on design responsibility*. New York, NY: Allworth Press, 20-24.
- Thomas, A. (2006) Design, poverty, and sustainable development. *Design Issues*, Vol. 22, No. 4, 54-65.
- Van de Poel, I. R., Zandvoort, H. & Brumsen, M. (2001) Ethics and engineering courses at Delft University of Technology: Contents, educational setup and experiences. *Science and engineering ethics*, Vol. 7, No. 2, 267-282.
- Whiteley, N. (1993) *Design for Society*. London: Reaktion.
- Yang, M.Y., You, M. & Han, C.Y. (2010) A study of industrial design students' employment preparation and choices in Taiwan. *Art, Design & Communication in Higher Education*, Vol. 9, No. 1, 21-40.
- Yang, M. Y. & You, M. (2010) A survey of career guidance needs of industrial design students in Taiwanese universities. *Asia Pacific Education Review*, Vol. 1, No. 4, 597-608.
- You, M. & Lee, Y. (2011) Design Ethics Education in Taiwan: A Study of Syllabi of Ethics-Related Courses. In: P.L.P. Rau (Ed.): *Internationalization, Design, HCII 2011, LNCS 6775*. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer-Verlag, 594-603.